

Extraction of Pigment from Prodigiosin and Carotenoid Bacteria for Dyeing of Textile Material

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Abstract:

Innovation in the manufacturing of textile dyes and auxiliary chemicals is nowadays essential tool to maintain the proper balance between the process and environment. Many attempts are taking place to develop sustainable and eco-friendly textile dyes and pigments to minimize the adverse effect on the environment. The present study is aimed to extract the pigment from prodigiosin and carotenoid bacteria which can be effectively used in the dyeing of cotton and polyester. Prodigiosin and carotenoid pigment was extracted from isolated soil samples by the bacterium *Serratia marcescens* and *Micrococcus luteus* respectively. The extracted pigments are biochemically characterized for confirmation of *Serratia marcescens* and *Micrococcus luteus*. Finally production of prodigiosin was optimized with respect to different parameters such as pH, temperature, incubation period.

Keywords: Carotenoid, dyes, *Micrococcus luteus*, Prodigiosin, *Serratia marcescens*, Thin layer Chromatography

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1. Introduction

Production of pigments from natural resources is nowadays important part of textile industry for production of sustainable and eco-friendly products to meet the demands of the customer. It is essential to explore various natural sources of dyes for maintaining the sustainability in the process and product and human ecology [1]. Production of pigments from the natural resources has many advantages because of their easy availability of cultivation technology. Pigments extracted from biological shows promising avenues due to its biodegradability and higher compatibility with the environment. Carotenoids is one of the most important pigment group comprising of yellow to orange-red variants, which are ubiquitous in nature with proven anti-carcinogenic and immune-modulation properties which is extracted from *Micrococcus luteus* bacteria and is harmless to mankind. This yellow pigment has shown promising UV-protective, antioxidant and antibacterial activity [2]. It clearly indicates the potential for exploration of these pigments as natural colouring agents in the textile industries and also as a U.V protective agent. The structure of M. Luteus is as shown in the Fig. 1

Figure 1 Structure of Carotenoid Pigment

Prodigiosin have health benefits antifungal, antibacterial, antimalarial, immune suppressive, anti-neoplastic and UV-resistant properties due to its chemical structure [3]. Fabric can be endowed with added value when the pigments are used as dyestuff which gives scarlet red colour variants and hence used in textile industries. This kind of pigments has been utilized to dye wool, polyester and acrylic fabrics with relatively good colour fastness, cotton can only be stained by the pigments without chemical mordants because of low affinity between prodigiosin molecular and cellulose. The structure of pigment is as shown in the Fig.2

Prodigiosin

Figure 2 Structure of prodigiosin pigment

Pigments extracted from prodigiosin and carotenoids can be used successfully to dye textile substrates and is completely eco-friendly.

In several studies, it has been reported that natural dyes are restarted to be used in colouring fabrics like cotton, silk, wool, nylon etc. [9]. Moreover, the growing interest on natural colorants also keeps the researchers busy to innovate convenient techniques to apply it on the textile substrate. The natural products have some drawbacks such as low predictability and extractability; very minute amount of dye might be extracted from kilograms of raw materials. To cope up with this hindrance, it is usually being suggested to apply appropriate selection techniques such as mutation or genetic engineering techniques for successful application of selected pigment at given process condition [9]. Microorganisms, for instance, bacteria as well as fungi are reported to be potent pigment producer. So, study with these creatures from environmental samples will unveil their hidden capability and application to mankind.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Collection of Soil Samples

Rhizosphere soil samples of banana tree were collected from the depth of 10 -15cm and kept in a sterilised glass container. The other laboratory chemicals such as methanol, concentrated HCl, concentrated ammonia solution, chloroform, acetone, ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate, lemon are used from the chemistry lab for the purpose of the extraction of pigments.

2.2 Isolation of Bacteria

The soil samples were serially diluted, 0.1ml of diluted samples from each dilution was spread over the Nutrient agar surface. Then the plates were incubated at 37° C for the period of 24 hrs, to observe the growth of morphologically distinct colonies. So, after this trail the experiment was carried out by using *Micrococcus luteus* which is also Carotenoid pigment producing bacteria with antibacterial property and yellow tone and studied all its aspects which are discussed further.

2.3 Presumptive test for prodigiosin pigment

The isolated organism was inoculated in the nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to observe the pigment production. The culture broth was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was suspended in 95% methanol to extract the pigment from the cells. The suspended pellet was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. Debris was removed and the supernatant was taken in two tubes. The content of the first tube was acidified with a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the second tube was alkalinized with a drop of concentrated ammonia solution. Then the colour change was observed.

2.4 Extraction of Pigment

Bacterial cultures from the liquid broth were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for the period of 15 minutes. The supernatant and cell pellet were extracted with acetone and ethyl acetate. Then the cell pellet was repeatedly centrifuged to obtain white pellet. The pigment extracts of ethyl acetate fraction and acetone fraction were evaporated separately in evaporating dishes at room temperature till the powder appears.

2.5 Purification of Pigment

Thin layer chromatography is a technique used to separate non-volatile mixtures. The prodigiosin pigment was separated using TLC plate coated with silica gel. In the chromatographic tank the developing solvent such as

chloroform, methanol and acetone (4:2:4v/v) was standardized and poured, then it was saturated with a filter paper soaking in the mobile phase. Then the Rf value of the chromatogram was found as 0.78 in the TLC plates.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Production of pigment in nutrient broth

In the present study nutrient broth was used for the production of the pigment, the yield of prodigiosin pigment on nutrient agar is 1326.07 mg/L. It was observed only after 96 hours of incubation. The bacterial growth in the agar plate is as shown in the Fig. 4 (a) and 9(b).

Figure 4 (a) - No bacterial growth for *S. Marcescenes* (b) *Micrococcus luteus* on nutrient agar

3.1 Presumptive test for prodigiosin pigment

The colour of the pigment is observed in solution of hydrochloric acid and alkaline ammonia solution. The colour of the solution found to be yellow after addition of hydrochloric acid and orange with the solution of ammonia.

3.2 Extraction of the Pigment

The supernatant obtained from the repeated centrifugation of bacterial cultures was extracted with ethyl acetate, petroleum ether and methanol. None of the extracts gave residual crude pigment. Then the pellet was extracted with acetone which yielded a residual crude pigment. The Carotenoid pigment is as shown in Fig. 4, and production is found to be 1326.07 mg/l on the nutrient agar.

Figure 4 - Carotenoid Pigment

4. Conclusion

In this study, a novel method of dyeing of textiles with pigments was carried out. It has been found that the pigments which are extracted from bacteria namely *Micrococcus luteus* and *Serratia marcescenes* shows highest yield at 30°C at 7 pH for 96 hours of incubation period. The pigment producing bacteria was isolated and characterized using nutrient broth. In large scale production, the pigment will make it an alternate to chemical dyes and further study can carried out in anticancer activity in human cervix carcinoma cells.

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